

Soils for Future under Global Challenges

UNCERTAINTY OF SOILGRIDS TESTED ON 1 200 000 SOIL DATA FROM NATIONAL SOIL FERTILITY CONTROL

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Abstract

SoilGrids is a system for digital soil mapping based on a global compilation of soil profile data (WoSIS) and environmental layers. SoilGrids provides global predictions for standard numeric soil properties (soil organic carbon (SOC), bulk density, cation exchange capacity (CEC), pH, soil texture fractions, and coarse fragments) at seven standard depths (0, 5, 15, 30, 60, 100, and 200 cm). For this study, accuracy assessment of provided data for pH in water, pH in KCl and SOC are being tested. The data used for this study are 200,000 georeferenced samples collected from the territory of central Serbia from a layer of 0-30 cm depth. To create a functional GIS database containing 1,200,000 data of basic chemical soil properties, obtained from 200,000 sample locations, harmonization was previously followed. The main parameter according to which the data are harmonized is the coordinate system or projection used during sampling. Soil data are used to test the uncertainty of SoilGrids in a way that the point data from layers were subtracted to make a difference in data that will represent the SoilGrids error. The results showed that the deviations for the pH in water are from -2.1 to +2.2 pH units, i.e., in over 95% of samples from -1.0 to +1.1 pH units. Deviations for the pH in KCl are from -2.7 to +2.6 pH units, i.e., in over 95% of samples from -1.4 to +1.2 pH units. Testing the accuracy of SOC showed deviations from -50 to +25 g kg⁻¹, i.e., the most common deviations from 0 to +10 g kg⁻¹ of SOC. Observing that soil sampling and its chemical analysis at the national level are time-consuming, digital soil mapping is considered valuable for fast making decisions over a large-scale territory. To improve the prediction of the spatial distribution of soil properties, it is important to enhance state-of-the-art machine learning methods to map the spatial distribution of soil properties at a farm-level scale.

Keywords: SoilGrids, uncertainty, pH, SOC